

A Review on Psychological Impact of Coronavirus Disease 2019

Aamir Mohsin, Rakhi Ahuja, Sreekiran CV

School of Allied Health Sciences, Delhi Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research University, New Delhi, India

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The rise of Covid-19 had acquired a noteworthy change the normal life of the common people. Largely individuals were limited within their home in a state of quarantine. The situation where people limited to stay in idle stage added with fear of Covid-19 induced major psychological effects in the population.

Evidence Acquisition: This paper intends to review the psychological impact of COVID-19 and its relationship with uneasiness, anxiety and depression were examined. For this paper more than 10 different studies have been reviewed using electronic data base, i.e., Google Scholar, PubMed, Medline, Elsevier, and Science Direct.

Result: Detailed review of studies pointed Covid-19 and other outbreak impacted the psychological health of population adversely. The psychological effects of anxiety, depression insomnia are found in diverse class of population along with mortalities of Covid-19.

Conclusion- Along with major morbidity and mortalities of the Covid-19 and other epidemic outbreak situations, psychological issues also need to be addressed with major concern through any proper psychological healing procedures including various traditional medicinal systems.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, Psychological affects, Corona Virus, Pandemic

1. INTRODUCTION

The rise of a novel form of coronavirus in Wuhan, China, is making a confounded and quickly advancing circumstance in everywhere throughout the world [1]. The World Health Organization has announced a few kinds of viral contaminations, and an enormous number of people are in peril for these diseases in various ways around the globe. Due to which most of the country are taking measurable precautions to reduce the burden of novel coronavirus. 2019 [2]. COVID-19 is developing irresistible malady previously distinguished in Wuhan; Corona virus (COVID-19) was at first detailed by China in late 2019 and spread to 13 nations by January 24, 2020. [3]. its belongings have not yet been settled, as the recognitions and testing results are developing rapidly, and leading to high mortality rate. Among normal manifestations of this disease are cough, fever, brevity of breath and at some point the diarrhoea can be referenced, Bats or snake are thought to be the natural host of COVID-19 [4]. COVID-19 forces irreversible mental effects on human social orders. Which incorporates total isolate and correspondence limitations that keep individuals from going out, dread of suffering from the disease, dread of getting tainted from the infection, uneasiness about losing friends and family, depression due to losing loved ones are a portion of the issues individuals should manage. The world has seen a several boundless episodes of acute respiratory ailments. For instance, SARS as a transmittable irresistible disease spread in 2003; at the same time, it was to a great extent oversaw by isolate measures, isolate is conceivable measure to break the disease pattern of COVID-19 however it's influencing mentally. [5]. COVID-19 creates fear and anxiety among people especially among affected countries

and people are living in fear. The vast majority of the individuals are experiencing gloom and mentally influenced on the grounds that they can't go outside for work and losing correspondence to other people [6]. During this pandemic most of the media are showing some depressive content and highlighting the long impacts of this disease that is actually causing anxiety and depression among people during lockdown and increasing concern among people [1]. In most of the country's social stability has been seriously affected by corona virus, 2019. Social stability refers to the range of life structure and reliable routine that is protective against situational hazards and due to which people are psychologically affected by COVID-19 [7]. The rate of anxiety and distress are higher among healthcare workers in comparison to general population because they are at higher risk to get infected, this condition causing anxiety, depression and lack of presence in work and hitting them psychologically [8]. Health professional and front line workers are vulnerable to both high risk of infection and mental health problem. They are also suffering from the fear of this novel COVID-19 to losing their families, friends and colleagues [9]. The consequences and effect of COVID-19 is affecting all aspects of human lives and causing distress. Common people are psychologically affected of this pandemic because they unable to do what they normally do in their life and these self-quarantine situation are actually causing anxiety, depression among them. The current pandemic of COVID-19 is serious resulting in a global burden [10]. The outbreak of COVID-19 is provoking the implementation of control measure which is made to control the outbreak of COVID -19 such as quarantine and other

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possible measures, but these possible measures are actually causing anxiety and affecting psychologically [11].

HISTORY OF PANDEMICS:

Antonine Plague was the first pandemic, which took place in 165-180 and nearly killed five million people. One of the serious diseases was plague which affects many people around the globe at different timeline. Among all types of flu's Spanish flu was the deadliest and it nearly killed 50 million people. HIV/AIDS is one such pandemic, where the first cases were witnessed in the year 1981 and still there is no cure. Though various pandemics took place, but mortality was reduced significantly due to improvement of health care infrastructure [12].

2. EVIDENCE ACQUISITION:

This paper intends to review the psychological impact of COVID-19 and its relationship with uneasiness, anxiety and depression were examined and how infectious disease outbreak are affecting psychologically to all human beings. Information used in this review was mainly obtained from scientific electronic academic journal database. For this paper more than 10 studies have been reviewed using electronic data base, i.e., Google Scholar, PubMed, Medline, Elsevier, and Science Direct.

RESULT:

In China, the cross-sectional study conducted by Wang et al. delineated, the Covid-19 pandemic had impacted psychologically for 53.8 % of total respondents. Among the population spent their time in their own home due to pandemic situation 75.2% of the population were worried about their family members. The level of anxiety, stress and depression appeared maximum in the population group of students and females [13]. During the outbreak of the infectious diseases, educated studying category also succumbed before Psychological issues. Al-Rabiaah et al. study of medical students in Saudi Arabia during the MERS outbreak reported 174 of total 174 responded students were undergoing various levels of anxiety. None were reported with severe anxiety, however, 134 (77%) students of total respondents were having minimal, 32 (18.4%) were having mild and 8 (4.6%) were having moderate anxiety. The study pointed knowledge score on MERS-COV as not significant [6]. A study by V.tucci et al. enquires into the various infectious disease of Ebola, ZIKA, and other infectious diseases, there communicated various mental health's in the study group. [14]. The cross-sectional a study by the Al Najjar NS et al. to assess psycho behavioural response among 358 individuals during MERS, 57.7% of total respondents were expressed moderate anxiety [15]. Studies point among the patients of Covid-19 anxiety and fear were very common. Anxiety, fear and other psychological issues intensified higher chances of mortality. And thus Covid-19 patients under treatment were conducted with continuous dynamic assessments for reducing Psychological impact [16]. The cross-sectional study was conducted of 180 medical staff with exposure to Covid-19 patients during January and February months in Wuhan by Han Xiao et al. Study figured out medical staffs possess stress and anxiety in a large level. [17].The study by Lee SM et al. analysed the effect of MERS outbreak among health workers and quarantine patients also pointed high post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms among health workers. Study of Psychological impact of quarantine on patients of other diseases, among studied patients 11% were

expressed of anxiety and 15.1% were expressed depression [18]. In a study by Jianbo Lai et al. among the population involved in health intervention like nurses, physicians, other health care workers, 50.4% of respondents reported depression. Other psychological issues like anxiety, insomnia, and distress were also present among health care workers. Anxiety was reported by 44.6% responded population, insomnia and distress were present in 34% and 71.5 % respectively [19]. The psychological traumatization was determined maximum in general public followed by non-front line workers and then in front line workers in the study conducted by Zhenyu Li et al. in china, where 214 general public, 234 front line workers and 292 non-front line workers were responded [20]. Large scale survey of 52,370 Chinese populations amid an outbreak of Covid-19 conducted by the JianyinQiu et al. from 36 provinces, 35% of total respondents experienced psychological distress. Also, 5.14% of 35% population were having severe distress [21].

CONCLUSION:

The unprecedented situation created by the surge of Covid-19 had compelled a larger portion of the population in the idle state of quarantine and isolation. Along with situation jeopardy of Covid-19 severity and mortality a large number of other psychological issues have been reported globally based on various studies. Among the reported issues, includes many psychological issues like anxiety, depression, insomnia etc.

To a limit, these psychological issues are contributed by the news of the global critical situation of the pandemic Covid-19. For some other in the quarantine, many are well worried about the other family members also. The psychological issues were largely reported in various studies, irrespective of their education and profession. Psychological effects due to situation were predominantly present in the common population, the medical workforce of both front line workers involved in direct intervention and not. Significantly psychological changes like insomnia, depression was reported in the front line workers. In a situation where the entire world is still in the race for developing a vaccine and an accurate treatment protocol for the Covid-19 and still uncertainty exists in the world. Hence, these psychological disorders of population also need to be addressed appropriately along with other major discussed morbidities of Covid-19. To counter psychological issues pushed complication of the population quarantined institutionally or in their residence, and others totally involved in health intervention including physicians, nurses, and other health workers need to be provided with an adequate psychological healing scientifically.

Many methods which reaching to the larger population, which include many traditional treatment methods can psychologically boost their morale and can prevent the rise of a parallel psychological disorders during current situation of Covid-19.

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